

Administration of Food & Drug Safety in Bihar

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Abstract: Health of the people in Bihar exposed to several known and unknown factors that contributing burden of diseases to great extent both actively and passively. Some major health challenges emerged due to changed life styles, consumerism, and cultural transformation across the state equally in urban and rural areas. New public health challenges emerged due to enhanced use of alcohol, substances, adulterated food, and drug, lack of safety measures, unhygienic conditions, exposure to undesired amount of radiation, and adverse vehicular conditions. The inadequate response of the *Public Health Administration* and *Food & Drug Safety Administration* in Bihar further contributing to the miseries. Use of insecticide, pesticide, carbide, oxytocin, alcohol, spurious drugs, adulterated food items including packaged foods all responsible for poor health of the population. On the one side sizeable population in Bihar find it hard to manage food with enough calorie on daily basis and on the reverse such factors was like a *multiple trouble*. It was so easy to manufacture and sale spurious or adulterated items in Bihar and so much so that a whole structure of makers, suppliers, and retailers of such items existed across the state. Several well-known brands also turned very doubtful. The situation demanded concerted, institutionalized, and sustainable action.

Key words: *Public Health Administration; Food and Drug Safety in Bihar*

FULL TEXT:

Life style and culture in Bihar changed so rapidly after Liberalization, Privatization, and Globalization (LPG) of the Indian economy started since early 1990s. The established social traditions and culture never eroded such fast since known history. Mobile phone, Computer, Laptops, LED TVs, and range of electronic and electrical gadgets became part of daily social transactions. Sweeping change also witnessed in dressing and food habits. In order to exploit the high demand several companies jumped into the ring. Contrary to that, a whole infrastructure of spurious manufacturer, supplier, and retailers also increased simultaneously. If big shopping malls and food courts came up then also numbers of five star hospitals, nursing homes, and diagnostic centres also came up in numbers. Bihar so far appeared failing in taking accurate cognizance of the problem and initiate appropriate action. Action that not taken as symbolic, without application of mind, customary, partisan however based upon core and dedicated principles of Food & Drug Safety norms and regulation. The failures of Public Health Administration could easily evident due to massive access and sale of adulterated and health hazardous goods. People even kept unaware about the fact the whole food chain corrupted including air, water, milk, fruits, vegetables, edible oils, chicken, eggs, packaged foods, drinks, and ready to serve kind of foods. In addition, the tendency of buying profits by majority of manufacturers, suppliers, and retailers could term responsible. The action of a Public Health Administration therefore could no way aimed at denouncing any good business however, it required logically taking correct instances and sticking with that.

No one could be sure about the quality of consumer goods with respect to health of the people. On rappers of those good although instructions and required charters for a

particular kind of goods manufacturer though mentioned however it could not sure how those charter or norms obliged and how those norms violated and to what extent. The lack of certifying, testing, and licensing authorities, laboratories still not came up in Bihar. The quality of consumer goods required tested periodically and scientifically with full lab certification having global acceptance of those certifications.

Food & Drugs Safety Administration has been one of the core component of the *Public Health Administration*. In several states of India, *Food & Drug Safety* norms regulated by different authorities however in many states including Bihar *Food & Drug Safety* regulated through authorities functioning under the aegis of Department of Health and Family Welfare. The Secretary level officer of the Department or Executive Director of the State Health Society Bihar also functioned as Food Safety Commissioner. However overall structure of Chief Drug Controller, Bihar also functioned under the aegis of Department of Health and Family Welfare, Bihar.

The overall mission, objectives, and mandate of the *Food & Drug Safety* administrators has been to protect, promote and enhance the health of people and to achieve this mission, it needed to be ensured that food is safe, wholesome and prepared in good and hygienic condition. Human, veterinary drugs and biological products are safe, stable, and efficacious and medical devices are safe and effective. Cosmetics are safe and stable. Any food and drug administration therefore has to ensure that these products comply with the law and FDA regulations. Noncompliance would promptly identified and corrected, and any unsafe or unlawful product removed from the market place and appropriate action taken against all concerned.

In Bihar, regulation of Drug Controller somehow established due to positioning and functioning of almost 56 drug inspectors across the state. Although they worked to the potential as it still required restructuring their functional ability. Contrary to drug safety, the food safety mechanism not well visible across the state however some news reports highlighted some raids here and there especially during certain occasions or mostly to make its appearance visible.

Drug Control and food safety laboratory made mandatory under various provisions of *Food & Drug Safety Acts* however in Bihar no such laboratory so far functional and this would say the sad story. In absence of any such laboratory fully and accordingly functional, the very root of *Food & Drug Safety* hanged in balance in Bihar. Such laboratory required testing samples in various sections received under Drugs & Cosmetics Act. It also required functioning, as Government Analyst as per the Drugs and Cosmetics Acts applicable to land as amended to date. District level licensing authorities, supervisors, drug, and food inspectors all required structured and restructured in Bihar. Technical officers well qualified for various medicines such as allopath, homeopathy, Ayurveda, and other medicines never put to position. Therefore, the functioning of licensing for manufacture, sale, carryout search, seizure, inspections, draw samples, and institution of prosecutions, all severely hampered. In addition, the scrutiny of the formulations of drugs for their efficacy, pharmacology, toxicology, etc and grant permission, rejection of permission for products that banned, irrational etc. also never streamlined in Bihar that would be major failure of the *Public Health Administration* in Bihar. Moreover, the overall licensing mechanism for drug manufacturing for the entire state, scrutiny of formulations, ingredients as per authoritative books and grant-rejection of the permissions all jeopardized, symbolic, or even shadowed. In fact, people hardly aware about food and safety norms and their functioning across Bihar.

One of the major task of any *Public Health Administration* used to take care of all kind of health determinants. The moral obligation was always in place to facilitate even safe drinking water, sanitation, and food items. No doubt that all could be reason, that Prime Minister *Sri Narendra Modi* realized the need of cleanliness. He then focused *Make in India* campaign with the tag line *Zero Defect and Zero Effect*. The zero effects means products must free from environmental and health hazards.

Contrary to every notions and norms if we find the sole food, adulteration lab of Bihar situated at Agamkuan, Patna entirely non-functional since long due to acute shortage of staff and equipment would definitely add to the misery. Even there was not a single reputed and trusted private lab in Bihar. The functioning of Food Safety Commissioner and Drug Controller Authorities in the State has been just symbolic. Casual raids on several installations sometimes

reported however, trails occurred in case of handful of offenders and punishment to any person so far rare. There could be large number of offenses of rules related to food and drug safety however there was a case of poor implementation of law due to shortage of staff regular raids on premises could not happen. Even there could no way adequately prosecuted and put to punishment.

The problem related to food and drug safety in Bihar has been tremendous. Several strong branded drugs also duplicated as per a general estimate. Several strong brands of edible oils, packaged food, cosmetics, and milk products highly adulterated and not safe for human consumption. The level of adulteration of those items had reached amazingly situation and no one in place to say what is adulterated and how? The very supply and marketing chain of even known brands crippled. Even a full-fledged parallel chain of manufacturer, supplier, and retailers of spurious or adulterated and duplicated items has been in place across the state. That has virtually taken the shape of cottage industries in several parts of Bihar. The damage to genuine business, health, and loss to public exchequer in this manner is immense. Common people not only losing money however, they endangered their life and health due to such high adulteration of consumable items.

THE RAMPANT USE OF OXYTOCIN IN BIHAR

Oxytocin used to be a hormonal secretion by the hypothalamus in all mammals. It acts primarily as a neuromodulator in the brain. An intravenous infusion of oxytocin used to tempt labor and to support labor in case of difficult parturition. Oxytocin also used in veterinary medicine to facilitate birth and to stimulate milk release. Oxytocin could be dangerous in high dosages for maternity and effects such as Subarachnoid hemorrhage, Increased heart rate, Decreased blood pressure, Cardiac arrhythmia and premature ventricular contraction, Impaired uterine blood flow, Pelvic hematoma, Afibrinogenemia, which can lead to hemorrhage and death, Anaphylaxis, Nausea and vomiting

Oxytocin in Bihar used by dairy farmers to produce milk from cattle without bothering for providing milk to small calf. It also used to ripen fruits and enlargement of size of vegetables especially pumpkin. The Bihar State Health Society (BSHS) imposed ban on over-the-counter sale of Oxytocin injections. Still it could find that most dairy farmers use Oxytocin to increase milk in pregnant cows. These injections also reported illegally manufactured in some parts of the state.

The large presence of oxytocin reported in Bihar also there were frequent complaints that cows and buffaloes were injected with Oxytocin for milk in addition to ripen fruits and vegetables. Even contaminated vials of oxytocin also used in Bihar whereby numerous cases of manufacturer compromising on quality.

USE OF CALCIUM CARBIDE

Calcium carbide could be carcinogenic however, it rampantly used in ripping of mangoes, banana, papaya, and other fruits and vegetables. It also used for lighting the place due to shortage of electricity. Carbide is skillfully packed into small sachets and scattered into the piles of mangoes either grown inside Bihar or imported from outside Bihar. The same process adopted for other fruits. . Sporadic media furore and official action against the use of this chemical compound with proven carcinogenic properties not deterred commission agents.

However, Janak Kishore, a farmer from Digha, Patna used to differ as he claimed that farmers never used carbide as they just used to sale crude mangoes or other fruits and in fact, agents used to rationalize the sale of fruits usually used carbide accordingly to the supply and demand. Use of carbide could curb effectively only by offering Minimum Support Price (MSP) to the farmers. Assured of MSP and insured against commission agents, the farmer could then allow the fruit to ripen on the tree before harvesting.

Calcium carbide (CaC_2) produced industrially from a mixture of lime and coke. Its main use industrially as the production of acetylene and calcium cyanamide. The pure material usually colorless, however pieces of technical-grade calcium carbide are grey or brown.

USE OF ALCOHOL AND TOBACCO PRODUCTS

Preventing drug abuse and excessive alcohol use could increase people's chances of living long, healthy, and productive lives. Excessive alcohol use included binge drinking (i.e., five or more drinks during a single occasion for men, four or more drinks during a single occasion for women), underage drinking, drinking while pregnant, and alcohol impaired driving. Drug abuse included any inappropriate use of pharmaceuticals (both prescription and over-the counter drugs) and any use of illicit drugs. Alcohol and other drug use can impede judgment and lead to harmful risk-taking behavior. Preventing drug abuse and excessive alcohol use bound to improve quality of life, academic performance, workplace productivity, and military preparedness; reduces crime and criminal justice expenses; reduces motor vehicle crashes and fatalities; and lowers health care costs for acute and chronic conditions.

Any Government as its Public Health Administration policy must initiate policy, plan, and action for preventing substance and alcohol use. Support must ensure by state to entire population for creation of environment highly unfriendly to users. It also required restricting access and banning the supply chain. Government could impose and regulate age restrictions. In Bihar, even children could find drinking especially homeless children. Employers could adopt policies that prevent use.

The very policy adopted by the Bihar government over the last few years resulted in massive increase in alcohol use in Bihar. However, government also failed to check and regulate properly the tobacco and substances use in Bihar.

Sale and use of various forms of tobacco and liquor so common in Bihar. Such thing promoted as part of culture turned really a great health hazards, as only no use policy would be beneficial. Alcohol use in Bihar also increased during last ten year alarmingly. However, no definite data on the prevalence rate of alcohol use however, certain general estimate said that prevalence rate in Indian varied between 167-340 per 1000 population. The overall substance use prevalence in India estimated at 6.0 per 1000 populations however in urban and rural terms that could expressed as 5.8 and 7.3 per 1000 population respectively (Pratima Murthy, 2011). The number of liquor vends allotted by the state government climbed to 5,467 in 2012/13 from 3,436 in 2006/07, according to official data. The jump was highest in rural areas, where the number of shops tripled to 2,360 from 779 during the same period. Liquor sales surged at a much faster pace. Consumption of country liquor multiplied while that of India-made foreign liquor (IMFL) increased almost five times and beer sales soared more than 11 times. All those resulted Bihar's excise revenue jumped to Rs 2,765 crore in 2012/13 from Rs 525 crore in 2007/08. The 40 per cent annualized growth made excise tax the fastest-growing segment in the state's revenue kitty. The share of excise duty in Bihar's own tax revenue increased to 17.65 per cent in 2012/13 from 10.33 per cent five years before. On the other hand, the share of other components such as sales tax slipped during the period.

Before 2005, 80 per cent of the liquor business was outside the revenue net. "The increase in revenue also resulted due to organizing the liquor trade. The state now allotted licenses for liquor shops through a lottery. A single license not granted. Depending on the area, it could allot licenses for two or three shops in a group mandated to sell IMFL or country liquor. In some cases, shops in rural and municipal areas tagged together. The state increased the annual license fee for bars from Rs 5 lakh to Rs 17 lakh in April 2013. The government also raised the minimum guaranteed quantity that vendors must procure from the state. Vendors' total monthly quota for IMFL raised to 3.91 million London proof liters (LPL) in 2013/14 from 2.90 million LPL the previous year. For country and spiced country liquor, the quota increased to 9.25 million LPL from 7.71 million LPL. Similarly, for beer the quota raised to 6 million bulk liters from 4 million bulk liters. LPL and bulk liters are units of alcohol measurement (Malhotra, 2014).

Tobacco, which annually kills 4.9 million people worldwide at present, estimated to take 10 million lives every year by 2020 (World Health Organization, 2000). Bihar has been front-runner in use of various forms of tobacco. Alcohol consumption in Bihar also rising alarmingly. According to GATS, study use of tobacco and liquor among women increasing day by day. Almost 6.5 percent women used bidi, followed by other smokeless tobacco products such as khani by 2.9 percent, betel 2.0 percent (Bhatia, 2013).

Various other forms of tobacco especially pouched forms such as Gutkha also considered harmful. A baby born of a woman using khaini and gutkka usually underweight by an average of 250 grams. Noted gynaecologist Dr Shanti Rai gave his opinion that if a pregnant woman use smoking, the carbon content may accumulate in the baby's windpipe that may cause respiratory problems as the brain lacks oxygen. According to surgeon Dr A A Hai "Like active smoking, passive smoking is also very harmful, both for the mother and the foetus.

Even a mother's life is at risk because smoking in pregnancy may cause miscarriage and other complications, including detachment of placenta and ectopic pregnancy (pregnancy that occurs outside the womb, a life-threatening condition for a woman), opine experts. However, there was no credible data yet at a DISHA centre Patna, during 2010-2011, provided treatment to 21 women admitted there out of the 2228 cases treated overall. While 17 cases were in the age group of 25-45, four were in the 45-60 age.

THE EDIBLE OIL

Not all edible oils considered good for human consumption in excessive. Even vegetable oils that rich in unsaturated fat also not always healthy for excessive use. Several kinds of edible oils advertised and marketed as healthy oils these days that mostly involved with high price. Bihar traditionally used mustard, teesi, til, groundnut oil mostly. Use of ghee, butter, and cream also has traditional aspects in Bihar. The consumption of dalada was restricted to mostly commercially however now refined oil mostly preferred across the state. Processed seed oils like soybean oil, sunflower oil, corn oil, canola oil, cottonseed oil, safflower oil and a few others even though they not really vegetables, these oils commonly referred to as "vegetable oils." These oils contained very large amounts of biologically active fats called Omega-6 polyunsaturated fatty acids that considered harmful in excess. Although that not applied to healthy plant oils like olive oil or coconut oil.

Studies found that Omega-3 and Omega-6 fatty acids could cause inflammation in the body that result in ache in various parts of body. However, Omega-6s considered pro-inflammatory, while Omega-3s anti-inflammatory. These different fatty acids compete with each other. The more Omega-6 you have, the more Omega-3 you need. The less Omega-6 you have, the less Omega-3 you need. It now believed that increased inflammation could contribute to various serious diseases, including cardiovascular disease, arthritis, depression, and even cancer.

Trans fats are unsaturated fats that modified to be solid at room temperature. These fats used to be highly toxic and are associated with an increased risk of various diseases, like heart disease, cancer, diabetes, and obesity. They considered so bad that even the governments around the world have started taking action, setting laws that

command food manufacturers to reduce the trans-fat content of their foods. However, a little known fact is that vegetable oils often contain massive amounts of Trans fats. In one study that looked at soybean and canola oils found on store shelves in the U.S., about 0.56 percent to 4.2 percent of the fatty acids in them were toxic Trans fats.

Several studies confirming that edible oil could be extremely harmful to health especially in had tremendous potential to increase cardiovascular, obesity, and diabetes. However according to me the real danger in Bihar could be the sale and use of adulterated edible oils.

CHINESE FOODS

In every corner of streets of Bihar especially in urban areas sale of Chinese food items such as Chow mien, Fried Rice, Chilies, and a range of other items became so common over the last 20 years. I still remember that very first time in Patna I came across such a food when one of my friend started in Maurya Complex food on wheel named Banjara. That food on wheel still run however number of other installations/ shops increased so rapidly in all parts of Bihar because food easy to cook, serve, and in great demand. Now Tibetan Momo also combined to that list. Although I never so crazy of Chinese food, yet I enjoy eating various those items more than once in a month.

There were some great health risk involved with intake of Chinese foods. Most of Chinese foods used borax and other chemicals that considered even carcinogenic and highly unsafe. Use of Monosodium Glutamate (MSG) also considered harmful. The issue of hygiene always involved with any outside home food items. The symptoms like diarrhea, loss of appetite, high heart rate, and dizziness so common side effects of those foods if cooked and served unhygienically. In fact, hygienic issue involved with all other food items. Chinese foods now also available in markets in form of sachet of soups and magic masalas.

MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS

Bihar remained traditionally rich in milk production and use of milk and milk products. Definitely, certain hygiene level involved with milk and milk products that involved the manner care performed extraction and process of milk. Hot milk, curd, butter, and ghee considered extremely good for health. Nowadays there increased used of cheese and cottage cheese ie paneer. If all those items prepared inside home then they considered safe. However if purchased from outside certain risks involved with them. In Bihar supply of milk and milk products largely trusted by big brands such as *Sudha* and *Amul*. *Sudha* chain more expanded, established, stable, and acceptable brand however *Amul* being Gujarat based almost making inroads. It required packaging and maintaining the cold chain evenly. Now milk used to sale that not destroy for many days even at normal temperature however, the manner that prepared could be risky. In addition, Bihar has also become a great market for adulterated milk and milk products. Milk

products used to be costly and most required items however; adulteration could most common in milk such as mixed with water or even could be synthetic milk made with chemicals. Even some great adulteration reported in all milk products such as *Khoya*, *Paneer*, and Cheese items. If consumed that could be extremely harmful to common people.

VEGETABLE AND FRUITS

Bihar has been one of the largest producer of fruits and vegetables however, most of them consumed locally. In any case, most of time potatoes, onions, and tomatoes imported from other states. The vegetable locally grown around Patna could have contamination because of irrigated with sewage water however, for the sake vegetables grown in distant parts of Bihar might consider safe although they mostly use insecticides and pesticides that could be harmful. The use of genetically modified seeds also started in Bihar for high yield. However, their adverse effects so far not adequately studied and presented. For longevity, vegetables now treated with gamma radiations and their ill effects not properly studied.

FROZEN AND READY TO EAT FOODS

I recently visited a mall in Patna and there came across a range of packed, frozen, and ready to cook foods. It just required to open the sachet and warm using boiled water or in an oven. The food most of time branded come to dates mentioned such as expiry and manufacture. Some foods items also declared that they contained any harmful preservatives. No doubt due to convenience and tiring process of cooking those ready to eat food being preferred despite high costs. I have also tasted several those foods on numerous occasions as they easy to cook and serve. Any bachelor could be extremely joyful however, their long use could be harmful, and I considered them as casual consumable. Even chicken, eggs, fish, seafood all required special attention before consumption. If not prepared properly they could induce viral and bacterial symptoms in body that could be fatal in some cases.

ELECTROMAGNETIC RADIATION

For better or worse, I could not tell however, we have selected to live and adjust with high radiation environment. The increasing number of mobiles, mobile towers, microwaves ovens, Induction Cooktops, and other Electrical- Electronic items had virtually put our life at more risk as never before. Microwaves in facts comparatively considered safer than X-Rays and Gamma Rays. During CT scan and MRI our body exposed to extremely dangerous high levels of radiation especially X-Rays. Several plastic products used in microwave cooking could sale in market using term Microwave Safe however they could not consider fully safe. For decades, scientists and consumers debated over the possible effects of non-ionizing electromagnetic radiation on living tissue. Since it's very difficult to sort out the various risks we might get

from fields emitted from power lines, cell phones, airplane flights, computers, clock radios, and of course microwave ovens. However, several studies found strong fields raise cancer rates and other problems, but what about the cumulative effect of small exposure, or effects on children required more studies that are precise. Even microwave cooking could be risky due to leakage of radiation and it considered at least 2 feet distance from the source as safe.

Several countries, as well as the International Electro technical Commission (IEC), the International Committee on Electromagnetic Safety (ICES) of the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) and the European Committee for Electro technical Standardization (CENELEC), set a product emission limit of 50 watts per square metre (W/m²) at any point 5 cm away from the external surfaces of the oven. In practice, emissions from modern domestic microwave ovens substantially below this international limit, and interlocked that prevent people exposed to microwaves while the oven on. Moreover, exposure decreases rapidly with distance; e.g. a person 50 cm from the oven receives about one one-hundredth of the microwave exposure of a person 5 cm away. These product emission limits defined for the purpose of compliance testing, not specifically exposure protection. The International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) published guidelines on exposure limits for the whole EMF part of the spectrum. Exposure guidelines in the microwave range set at a level that prevents any known adverse health effect. Exposure limits for workers and for the public set well below levels where any hazardous heating occur from microwave exposure. The emission limit for microwave ovens mentioned above consistent with the exposure limits recommended by ICNIRP (WHO, 2005).

USE OF PESTICIDES AND INSECTICIDE

Life of people either in rural or urban areas of Bihar considered at high risk due to massive used of insecticide and pesticide. The harmful chemicals already entered so deep in the food chain and ecosystem. The air, water, and soil all showed alarmingly high assimilation of harmful chemicals such DDT.

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